
Multi-Objective Optimization for Power Conversion System Design in Grid-Connected Hybrid Energy Storage System

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Abstract: The increasing integration of renewable energy sources and energy storage systems into the electrical grid demands the development of high-performance power conversion technologies. In this context, the design of efficient and reliable power conversion systems (PCS) is crucial for the integration of these energy sources. The use of optimization tools facilitates the selection of power conversion architectures and converter topologies that enhance overall efficiency and reliability while reducing development time. This paper presents an advanced optimization tool developed for designing the dc-ac PCS of HESS, which integrates a lithium-titanate-oxide (LTO) battery and an aqueous-organic-redox-flow (AORF) battery for grid connection. Four conversion architectures are explored with different degrees of dc-dc and dc-ac module parallelization. A set of optimization problems is defined to obtain the Pareto front of solutions for each architecture, resulting in different trade-offs between the system's performance metrics.

1. Introduction

Hybrid energy storage systems (HESS) have become a popular solution to address the intermittency of renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind [1–4]. The design of efficient and reliable power conversion systems (PCS) represents a key challenge in the integration of the HESS into the grid. Optimization processes are often used in order to identify the optimum PCS design in terms of efficiency, capital and operational costs, power density, and other performance indicators [5–7]. These processes enable a systematic evaluation of trade-offs, obtaining a PCS ensuring good results in the performance indicators.

This paper presents an advanced optimization tool developed for designing the optimum power conversion architecture of the dc-ac PCS of a HESS integrating a lithium-titanate-oxide (LTO) battery and an aqueous-organic-redox-flow (AORF) battery to the grid. The optimization process presented in this paper focuses on comparing the performance of four different power conversion architectures in terms of power losses and cost.

The candidate conversion architectures use a two-stage power conversion: the first stage comprises dc-dc converters interfacing the dc ports of the LTO and AORF batteries, while the second stage features dc-ac converters connecting the dc bus of the dc-dc stage to the grid. Dual Active Bridge (DAB) converters are used in the first power conversion stage, featuring bidirectional power flow capability, high performance and galvanic isolation [8–12], and three-phase PWM dc-ac converters are used in the second stage.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the candidate power conversion architectures. Then, Section 3 introduces the electrical model of the HESS batteries and power converters. Section 4, Section 5, Section 6 and Section 7 describe the losses, thermal, reliability, and cost models for the PCS. Then, Section 8 presents the multi-objective optimization function and the results of the optimization process. Finally, Section 9 discusses the implications of the optimization tool.

2. Candidate power conversion architectures

Figure 1 shows the four candidate conversion architectures. Architecture A is the most parallelized architecture, using three parallel dc-dc converters and a separate dc-ac converter for each battery. In contrast, Architecture D presents the lowest level of

parallelization, with a single dc-dc converter per battery and a single dc-ac converter connecting the common dc bus to the ac grid. Architectures B and C offer intermediate levels of parallelization: Architecture B uses a single dc-ac converter and three dc-dc converters per battery, and Architecture C employs a single dc-dc converter and a dc-ac converter per battery. These four architectures provide different configurations for optimizing system performance.

Figure 1. Candidate conversion architectures.

3. HESS electrical model

3.1. LTO and AORF batteries

LTO and AORF batteries are modeled as a constant and ideal voltage source connected in series to a resistor (Figure 2). Table 1 shows the electrical parameters of the HESS batteries. Both batteries are configured to operate at their nominal voltage and power ratings. The ideal voltage sources V_{LTO} and V_{AORF} represent the nominal voltage of the batteries. When operating at nominal power and voltage, the internal resistance voltage drop is 5% for the LTO battery and 19% for the AORF battery.

Figure 2. LTO and AORF batteries electrical model.

Table 1. Electrical ratings of the HESS batteries.

Battery	Nominal voltage [V]	Nominal power [kW]	Internal resistance [mΩ]
LTO	330	50	100.8
AORF	50	9	42.6

3.2. DAB converter

The DAB converters used in the analyzed architectures exhibit a dual-sided configuration: the low voltage (LV) side interfaces with the energy storage elements (LTO and AORF batteries), while the high voltage (HV) side is connected to the common dc-link shared with the dc-ac inverter modules. The DAB (Figure 3) features two active bridges connected through a high-frequency (HF) transformer, where power flow is controlled by implementing single phase-shift modulation between the bridges' ac output voltages. The phase-shift angle φ induces a current through the converter's high-frequency (HF) inductor, L , enabling bidirectional power flow control.

Figure 3. Electrical scheme of the DAB.

Figure 4. Electrical scheme of the DAB.

Figure 4 depicts the DAB currents and voltages. The instantaneous current through the inductor, i_L , is defined over a switching period as

$$i_L(\theta) = \begin{cases} \frac{V_{LV} + \frac{V_{HV}}{n}}{2\pi f_{DAB} L} \theta - \frac{V_{LV} \frac{\pi}{2} + \frac{V_{HV}}{n} \left(\varphi - \frac{\pi}{2}\right)}{2\pi f_{DAB} L}, & 0 \leq \theta < \varphi \\ \frac{V_{LV} - \frac{V_{HV}}{n}}{2\pi f_{DAB} L} (\theta - \varphi) + \frac{V_{LV} \left(\varphi - \frac{\pi}{2}\right) + \frac{V_{HV}}{n} \frac{\pi}{2}}{2\pi f_{DAB} L}, & \varphi \leq \theta < \pi \\ -\frac{V_{LV} + \frac{V_{HV}}{n}}{2\pi f_{DAB} L} (\theta - \pi) + \frac{V_{LV} \frac{\pi}{2} + \frac{V_{HV}}{n} \left(\varphi - \frac{\pi}{2}\right)}{2\pi f_{DAB} L}, & \pi \leq \theta < \pi + \varphi \\ -\frac{V_{LV} - \frac{V_{HV}}{n}}{2\pi f_{DAB} L} (\theta - \pi - \varphi) - \frac{V_{LV} \left(\varphi - \frac{\pi}{2}\right) + \frac{V_{HV}}{n} \frac{\pi}{2}}{2\pi f_{DAB} L}, & \pi + \varphi \leq \theta \leq 2\pi \end{cases}, \quad (1)$$

where f_{DAB} is the converter's switching frequency and n is the inverse of the transformer's turns ratio, rt . The LV and HV side instantaneous currents, i_{LV} and i_{HV} , are defined as

$$i_{\text{LV}}(\theta) = \begin{cases} \frac{V_{\text{LV}} + \frac{V_{\text{HV}}}{n}}{2\pi f_{\text{DAB}}L} \theta - \frac{V_{\text{LV}} \frac{\pi}{2} + \frac{V_{\text{HV}}}{n} \left(\varphi - \frac{\pi}{2}\right)}{2\pi f_{\text{DAB}}L}, & 0 \leq \theta < \varphi \\ \frac{V_{\text{LV}} - \frac{V_{\text{HV}}}{n}}{2\pi f_{\text{DAB}}L} (\theta - \varphi) + \frac{V_{\text{LV}} \left(\varphi - \frac{\pi}{2}\right) + \frac{V_{\text{HV}}}{n} \frac{\pi}{2}}{2\pi f_{\text{DAB}}L}, & \varphi \leq \theta < \pi \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$i_{\text{HV}}(\theta) = \begin{cases} -\frac{V_{\text{LV}} + \frac{V_{\text{HV}}}{n}}{2\pi f_{\text{DAB}}Ln} \theta + \frac{V_{\text{LV}} \frac{\pi}{2} + \frac{V_{\text{HV}}}{n} \left(\varphi - \frac{\pi}{2}\right)}{2\pi f_{\text{DAB}}Ln}, & 0 \leq \theta < \varphi \\ \frac{V_{\text{LV}} - \frac{V_{\text{HV}}}{n}}{2\pi f_{\text{DAB}}Ln} (\theta - \varphi) + \frac{V_{\text{LV}} \left(\varphi - \frac{\pi}{2}\right) + \frac{V_{\text{HV}}}{n} \frac{\pi}{2}}{2\pi f_{\text{DAB}}Ln}, & \varphi \leq \theta < \pi \end{cases}, \quad (3)$$

and the active power transferred by the converter from the LV side to the HV side is

$$P_{\text{DAB}} = \frac{V_{\text{LV}}^2}{2\pi f_{\text{DAB}}L} d \varphi \left(1 - \frac{|\varphi|}{\pi}\right), \quad (4)$$

where $d = V_{\text{HV}} / (V_{\text{LV}}n)$ is the LV-side-referred dc-voltage gain of the converter.

Due to the internal resistance of the battery, V_{LV} decreases as P_{DAB} increases, as described by

$$V_{\text{LV}}(P_{\text{DAB}}) = \frac{V_{\text{bat}} + \sqrt{V_{\text{bat}}^2 - 4R_{\text{bat}}P_{\text{DAB}}}}{2}. \quad (5)$$

From [8], when $d = 1$, zero-voltage switching (ZVS) is achieved during the switches turn-on transitions at both sides of the converter across the full power range. Soft-switching transitions result in reduced switching losses and improved efficiency, particularly at high switching frequencies. For $d \neq 1$, soft switching is lost in the low-power range, leading to increased switching losses; i.e., hard switching, which negatively affects efficiency. Additionally, when $d \gg 1$ or $d \ll 1$, the converter conduction and switching losses increase due to increased RMS currents in the switches and magnetic components, as well as higher switching currents in the switches. Figure 5 shows the relation between φ and P_{DAB} for the AORF DAB converter. When rt is set for $V_{\text{LV}}(P_{\text{DAB,nom}})$ (Section 3.2), the converter will feature hard-switching losses in the low-power range. This is avoided when rt is set for $V_{\text{LV}}(P_{\text{DAB,nom}}/2)$ (Section 3.2). Although setting rt for $V_{\text{LV}}(P_{\text{DAB,nom}})$ allows lower conduction and switching losses in the high-power range, efficiency is greatly diminished in the low-power range. The described performance characteristics are also featured in the LTO DAB converter.

Thus, to maintain a fairly constant efficiency in the whole power range, rt is defined for AORF and LTO DAB converters as

$$rt = \frac{1}{n} = \frac{V_{\text{LV}}(P_{\text{DAB,nom}}/2)}{V_{\text{HV}}}. \quad (6)$$

Figure 5. AORF-DAB-converter relation between the phase shift and the transferred power considering the battery voltage drop (blue line). Shaded areas indicate hard-switching regions.

3.3. dc-ac converter

Figure 6 depicts the electrical scheme of the three-phase PWM dc-ac converter, used in the second stage of the candidate conversion architectures to connect the high-voltage dc bus to the ac grid. This converter has bidirectional power flow capability and is controlled using the sinusoidal pulse-width modulation (SPWM) technique.

Figure 6. Electrical scheme of the dc-ac.

The fundamental component of the phase voltages synthesized by the dc-ac converter are

$$\begin{cases} v_{a,1}(\theta) = V_{inv,1} \sin(\theta + \varphi_{V,inv,1}) \\ v_{b,1}(\theta) = V_{inv,1} \sin\left(\theta - \frac{2\pi}{3} + \varphi_{V,inv,1}\right) \\ v_{c,1}(\theta) = V_{inv,1} \sin\left(\theta + \frac{2\pi}{3} + \varphi_{V,inv,1}\right) \end{cases}, \quad (7)$$

where $V_{inv,1}$ is defined as

$$V_{inv,1} = m_a \frac{V_{HV}}{2}, \quad (8)$$

m_a is the modulation index and $\varphi_{V,inv,1}$ is the phase shift between the converter reference phase voltages and the grid voltages.

Considering the converter ac-side phase currents to be sinusoidal, these are defined as

$$\begin{cases} i_a(\theta) = I_1 \sin(\theta + \varphi_{L,inv,1}) \\ i_b(\theta) = I_1 \sin\left(\theta - \frac{2\pi}{3} + \varphi_{L,inv,1}\right) \\ i_c(\theta) = I_1 \sin\left(\theta + \frac{2\pi}{3} + \varphi_{L,inv,1}\right) \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where I_1 is the grid currents fundamental component amplitude and $\varphi_{L,inv,1}$ is the grid currents phase shift with respect to the grid voltages.

The active and reactive power transferred by the converter to the grid are

$$\begin{cases} P = \frac{3}{2} V_{\text{grid}} I_1 \cos(\varphi_{\text{inv}}) \\ Q = \frac{3}{2} V_{\text{grid}} I_1 \sin(\varphi_{\text{inv}}), \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

respectively, where V_{grid} is the amplitude of the grid phase voltages and $\varphi_{\text{inv}} = -\varphi_{L,inv,1}$ is the power-factor angle at the grid.

4. PCS losses model

This section presents the model used in the optimization process to compute the power losses of the components of the PCS. The model accounts for losses in semiconductors, magnetic elements, and capacitors, providing a comprehensive assessment of system efficiency.

4.1. Semiconductor losses

The semiconductor devices considered for the four converter architectures are Si and SiC MOSFETs for the DAB LV side, and SiC MOSFETs for the DAB HV side and the dc-ac converter. As the DAB converter works under soft-switching conditions, and the MOSFET body diode turn-on switching losses are considered negligible, semiconductor losses are limited to MOSFET conduction and turn-off losses, as well as body diode conduction losses. In the dc-ac converter, losses include MOSFET conduction, turn-on, turn-off, and reverse diode conduction and turn-off losses.

4.1.1. Conduction losses

MOSFET conduction losses (for both Si and SiC devices) consist of on-state conduction losses, proportional to the drain-to-source on-state resistance $r_{ds,on,k}$, and reverse conduction losses in the MOSFET body diode, determined by the on-state diode voltage drop $V_{f0,k}$, and the diode equivalent resistor $r_{f,k}$. These parameters are temperature-dependent and are linearly adjusted to the junction temperature at the operating point, $T_{j,k}$.

Then, the on-state conduction losses for the k MOSFET device are defined as

$$P_{\text{cond,MOS,on-state,tot}}(T_{j,k}) = \sum_k r_{ds,on,k}(T_{j,k}) \cdot I_{\text{rms,MOS},k}^2, \quad (11)$$

where $I_{\text{rms,MOS},k}$ is the rms current flowing through the k MOSFET device.

In reverse conduction mode the source-to-drain voltage is defined as

$$v_{sd,k}(t) = r_{ds,on,k}(T_{j,k}) \cdot i_{\text{MOS},k}(t) \quad (12)$$

where $i_{\text{MOS},k}(t)$ is the reverse current flowing through the channel resistance.

In the third quadrant, reverse current may flow through either the channel resistance or the body diode, and the portion of current flowing through each path is not constant. Consequently, third quadrant conduction losses are analyzed in two distinct time intervals.

Linearizing the body diode's third quadrant characteristics using V_{f0} and r_f reveals that no current flows through the parasitic diode when $V_{sd} \leq V_{f0}$. Under these conditions, the entire current flows through the MOSFET channel, and the source-to-drain voltage is defined as

$$v_{sd,k}(t) = r_{ds,on,k}(T_{j,k}) \cdot i_{D,k}(t) \quad (13)$$

where $i_{D,k}(t)$ is the total reverse current in the device, in this case flowing entirely through channel resistance $r_{ds,on,k}$.

The instant t_{lim} is defined as the time when $V_{sd} = V_{f0}$, and the source-to-drain voltage is

$$r_{ds,on,k}(T_{j,k}) \cdot i_{D,k}(t_{lim,k}) = V_{f0,k} \quad (14)$$

When $V_{sd} > V_{f0}$, that is $i_{D,k}(t) > i_{D,k}(t_{lim})$, a portion of the current flows through the body diode, while the remainder flows through the MOSFET channel. In this case,

$$i_{D,k}(t) = i_{MOS,k}(t) + i_{diode,k}(t) \quad (15)$$

where $i_{diode,k}(t)$ is the reverse current flowing through the body diode. Also, the diode anode-to-cathode voltage is equal to the MOSFET source-to-drain voltage. Therefore,

$$V_{f0,k} + i_{diode,k}(t) \cdot r_{f,k}(T_{j,k}) = r_{ds,on,k}(T_{j,k}) \cdot i_{MOS,k}(t) \quad (16)$$

It is possible then to determine the expression of the instantaneous current flowing through the body diode and through the MOSFET channel during reverse conduction,

$$i_{MOS,k}(t) = \frac{V_{f0,k}(T_{j,k}) + i_{D,k}(t) \cdot r_{f,k}(T_{j,k})}{r_{ds,on,k}(T_{j,k}) + r_{f,k}(T_{j,k})} \quad (17)$$

$$i_{diode,k}(t) = \frac{i_{D,k}(t) \cdot r_{ds,on,k}(T_{j,k}) - V_{f0,k}(T_{j,k})}{r_{ds,on,k}(T_{j,k}) + r_{f,k}(T_{j,k})}, \quad (18)$$

and the reverse conduction losses are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} P_{cond,MOS,rev,tot} = & \sum_k (r_{ds,on,k} \cdot \frac{1}{\Delta t_{1,k}} \cdot \int_{t_i,k}^{t_{lim,k}} i_{D,k}(t)^2 \cdot dt + \\ & r_{ds,on,k} \cdot \frac{1}{\Delta t_{2,k}} \cdot \int_{t_{lim,k}}^{t_{f,k}} i_{MOS,k}(t)^2 \cdot dt + \\ & r_{f,k} \cdot \frac{1}{\Delta t_2} \cdot \int_{t_{lim,k}}^{t_{f,k}} i_{diode,k}(t)^2 \cdot dt + V_{f0,k} \cdot \frac{1}{\Delta t_2} \cdot \int_{t_{lim,k}}^{t_{f,k}} i_{diode,k}(t) \cdot dt) \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where Δt_1 is the time interval during which $V_{sd} \leq V_{f0}$, and Δt_2 is the time interval during which $V_{sd} > V_{f0}$, and t_i and t_f are the instants when the reverse conduction starts and ends.

$$P_{cond,MOS,tot} = P_{cond,MOS,on-state,tot} + P_{cond,MOS,rev,tot} \quad (20)$$

4.1.2. Si MOSFET switching losses

Datasheets for Si MOSFETs often omit explicit information on energy loss per switching event. Then, the energy lost during a turn-off transition can be approximated as

$$E_{sw,off,k} = \int_0^{t_{ru}+t_{fi}} v_{ds,k}(t) \cdot i_{d,k}(t) \cdot dt = V_{DD,k} \cdot I_{D,k} \cdot \frac{t_{ru,k} + t_{fi,k}}{2}, \quad (21)$$

where $I_{D,k}$ is the switching current, $V_{DD,k}$ is the blocking voltage and $t_{ru,k}$ and $t_{fi,k}$ are the voltage rising time and current falling time during the turn-off transition, respectively. Then, the turn-off losses for Si MOSFET devices are defined as

$$P_{sw,off,MOS,tot} = f_{sw,k} \sum_k E_{sw,off,k} \quad (22)$$

4.1.3. SiC MOSFET switching losses

Datasheets for SiC MOSFET devices typically specify reference values for turn-on and turn-off energy loss, $E_{sw,on,ref,k}$ and $E_{sw,off,ref,k}$ respectively, and for the body diode turn-off energy loss, $E_{sw,rec,ref,k}$. These values are provided under defined operating conditions, including a reference drain-to-source voltage, $V_{ds,ref,k}$, switching current $I_{sw,ref,k}$, gate resistor $R_{G,ref,k}$ and junction temperature $T_{ref,k}$. Using the information provided in the datasheets, the MOSFET turn-on and turn-off energy losses and the body diode turn-off losses are adjusted to the actual operating conditions using linear regressions. Then, the switching losses for SiC MOSFET devices are computed as

$$P_{sw,on/off/rec,SiC,tot} = \sum_k f_{sw,k} \cdot E_{sw,on/off/rec,k} \left(T_{j,k}, V_{ds,k}, I_{sw,k}, R_{G,k} \right). \quad (23)$$

4.2. Magnetic elements losses

Magnetic element losses can be categorized into winding dc copper losses, winding ac copper losses, and magnetic core losses. Winding dc losses arise from the Joule effect caused by dc and low-frequency current components in the conductor material, such as copper. In contrast, winding ac losses result from the skin and proximity effects, which reduce the effective cross-section for current flow at high frequencies, increasing Joule losses. Finally, high-amplitude ac currents in the winding can induce considerable magnetic core losses due to energy dissipation within the core.

In DAB inductors (L_{sx}) and transformers (T_{ax}), only ac copper losses and magnetic core losses are considered due to the high-frequency currents and voltages without dc bias. Conversely, the filter inductors (L_{lx}) in the dc-ac converter are designed to achieve low current total harmonic distortion (THD), resulting in low-frequency currents with minimal high-frequency ripple and no dc bias. Consequently, these inductors present dc copper losses and magnetic core losses, with ac copper losses being negligible.

4.2.1. Conduction losses

Losses on a magnetic device with k windings due to the dc and low frequency components of the winding current are modeled as

$$P_{dc} = \sum_{j=1}^k R_{dc,j} \cdot I_j^2 \quad (24)$$

where I_j is the rms current of winding j and

$$R_{dc,j} = \rho_j \cdot \frac{n_j \cdot MLT}{npw_j \cdot A_{w,j}} \quad (25)$$

is winding j dc resistance, where ρ_j and $A_{w,j}$ are winding j wire resistivity and cross-sectional area, respectively, n_j and MLT are the number of turns and the mean length turn of winding j , respectively, and npw_j is the number of wire conductors connected in parallel in winding j .

The ac copper losses in winding j are defined as

$$P_{ac,j} = \sum_{m_j=1}^{M_j} P_{ac,m_j} = I_{1,j}^2 \cdot R_{dc,j} \cdot R_{ac,j}. \quad (26)$$

where R_{ac} is the winding ac resistance, which value is obtained from the magnetic element dimensions and material as discussed in [13].

4.2.2. Core losses

Magnetic losses in the core material arise from two primary mechanisms: hysteresis losses, associated with energy dissipation in the magnetic-field hysteresis loop, and eddy

current losses, resulting from the induction of currents within the electrically conductive core material. These losses can be effectively modeled using the Steinmetz equation as

$$P_{Fe} = K_{Fe0} \cdot f_1^{\zeta} \cdot \Delta B^{\beta} \cdot N_c \cdot A_c \cdot l_m, \quad (27)$$

where K_{Fe0} , ζ , and β are parameters coming from selected magnetic material, N_c is the number of stacked cores, A_c is the cross-sectional area of a single magnetic core, l_m is the core magnetic path length, and ΔB is half of the core flux density swing in the hysteresis cycle, defined as

$$\Delta B = \frac{\gamma}{2 \cdot n_j \cdot N_c \cdot A_c}, \quad (28)$$

where γ is the volts-seconds applied to any of the windings, defined as the integral of the voltage over half a period.

4.3. Capacitor losses

Capacitor losses are mainly caused by joule-effect losses on its parasitic resistance and can be modeled as

$$P_{cap} = ESR \cdot I_c^2 \quad (29)$$

where ESR is the capacitor equivalent series resistance and I_c is the capacitor rms current.

5. PCS thermal model

This section introduces the thermal model used in the optimization process to compute the heat dissipation of PCS components. The model includes the heat dissipation in semiconductors, magnetic elements and capacitors.

5.1. Semiconductors heat dissipation

To dissipate the heat generated by MOSFET power losses, a heatsink is attached to the devices. MOSFETs may be individually packaged or grouped into modules, with each discrete device having its own heatsink or sharing one when connected in parallel. For module-based configurations, one heatsink is used per module. Heat flows from the chip junction to the heatsink and then to the ambient air, with thermal resistances defined by junction-to-case ($R_{th,j-c}$), case-to-heatsink ($R_{th,c-h}$), and heatsink-to-ambient ($R_{th,h-a}$).

Power losses in each semiconductor depend on its junction temperature. Since all semiconductors attached to a heatsink share the same $R_{th,j-c}$, $R_{th,c-h}$, and power losses, the junction ($T_{j,n}$) and case ($T_{j,c}$) temperatures of a semiconductor device n are defined using the following system of linear equations

$$\begin{cases} P_{cond,n} + P_{sw,n} = f(T_{j,n}) \\ P_{cond,1}(T_{j,1}) = P_{cond,2}(T_{j,1}) = \dots = P_{cond,n}(T_{j,n}) \\ P_{sw,1}(T_{j,1}) = P_{sw,2}(T_{j,2}) = \dots = P_{sw,n}(T_{j,n}) \\ R_{th,j-c,1} = R_{th,j-c,2} = \dots = R_{th,j-c,n} \\ R_{th,c-h,1} = R_{th,c-h,2} = \dots = R_{th,c-h,n} \\ T_{c,n} = T_a + R_{th,h-a} \cdot N \cdot (P_{cond,1} + P_{sw,1}) \\ T_{j,n} = T_{c,n} + (R_{th,j-c,n} + R_{th,c-h,n}) \cdot (P_{cond,n} + P_{sw,n}) \end{cases}, \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, N, \quad (30)$$

where N is the number of semiconductors attached to the heatsink, $P_{cond,n}$ and $P_{sw,n}$ are the conduction and switching losses of semiconductor n , and T_a is the ambient temperature.

5.2. Magnetics heat dissipation

The thermal model for the magnetic elements includes a single thermal resistance that dissipates heat from power losses in the copper wires and magnetic core. From [14,15], the temperature rise above ambient depends on the surface area in contact with air, considering both the magnetic core and copper wires, and is defined as

$$\Delta T_k = \left(\frac{P_{\text{core},k} + P_{\text{copper},k}}{10 \cdot S_{\text{magnetic},k}} \right)^{0.833}, \quad (31)$$

where $P_{\text{core},k}$ and $P_{\text{copper},k}$ are expressed in W, respectively, and $S_{\text{magnetic},k}$ is the k^{th} magnetic element surface area expressed in m^2 . Since the model consists of a single thermal resistance, the temperature at the magnetic core and copper wires is the same and equal to

$$T_{\text{magnetic},k} = T_a + \Delta T_k. \quad (32)$$

The compound thermal resistance of the k^{th} magnetic element is then given by

$$R_{\text{th,magnetic},k} = \frac{\left(\frac{P_{\text{core},k} + P_{\text{copper},k}}{10 \cdot S_{\text{magnetic},k}} \right)^{0.833}}{P_{\text{core},k} + P_{\text{copper},k}}. \quad (33)$$

5.3. Capacitors heat dissipation

The thermal model of the capacitors includes a fixed thermal resistance, $R_{\text{th,cap},0}$, and a component $R_{\text{th,cap},1}$ that varies with the fan air speed u_{wind} when forced convection is used. $R_{\text{th,cap},1}$ is maximum when no fan is used and decreases as wind speed increases. The total thermal resistance is then defined as

$$R_{\text{th,cap}}(u_{\text{wind}}) = R_{\text{th,cap},0} + R_{\text{th,cap},1}(u_{\text{wind}}), \quad (34)$$

where $R_{\text{th,cap}}$, $R_{\text{th,cap},0}$ and $R_{\text{th,cap},1}$ are expressed in K/W and u_{wind} is expressed in m/s. Therefore, the temperature of a capacitor is expressed as

$$T_{\text{cap}} = T_a + \left(R_{\text{th,cap},0} + R_{\text{th,cap},1}(u_{\text{wind}}) \right) \cdot P_{\text{cap}}. \quad (35)$$

6. PCS reliability model

The reliability assessment of the candidate power conversion architectures accounts for the potential failure of key power converter components, including Si and SiC MOSFETs, capacitors, inductors, and transformers. The failure rates of these devices are estimated based on the guidelines provided in [16] and depend on the operating conditions of the components and their design parameters, including material composition, power and voltage ratings, capacitance, and operating frequency.

In a given architecture, a converter is considered to have failed, and its operation is halted if any of its constituent components fail. Consequently, the failure rate of a converter within a specific architecture and group is computed as the sum of the failure rates of its components; i.e.,

$$\lambda_{x,g} = \sum_k \lambda_{x,g,k}, \quad (36)$$

where $\lambda_{x,g,k}$ is the failure rate of component k in converter group g in architecture x . It is assumed that the failure of a single converter does not lead to cascading failures across the other converters, due to the implementation of adequate protection measures, such as fuses, circuit breakers, and converters housed in separate fire-resistant enclosures.

To evaluate the reliability of each conversion architecture, the corresponding Markov models are derived. The Markov chains, illustrated in Figure 7, provide a comprehensive

framework for evaluating the reliability of these architectures. The reliability analysis highlights key differences in fault tolerance. In architectures C and D, the failure of any dc-dc or dc-ac converter causes a system shutdown, resulting in two operational states: fully operational (x_0) or halted (x_1). Conversely, architectures A and B, comprising two groups of three parallel dc-dc converters, can tolerate up to one dc-dc converter failure per group, operating at partial load under such conditions, and the associated dc-ac converters function at partial load as well. Consequently, the failure rate of the dc-ac converters varies according to the operational state of the architecture system ($s \in \{0, 1, \dots\}$). These architectures feature five states, ranging from fully operational (x_0) to halted (x_4), with intermediate states x_1 and x_2 corresponding to a single dc-dc converter failure in Group 1 or Group 2, respectively, and x_3 representing failures in one converter from each group, all resulting in partial load operation.

On all architectures, repair of the converters is considered. Since repair time is usually dominated by the time spent in the failure assessment and travel to the HESS location, repair rate (λ_R) is a constant value independent of the failed converter, number of failed units, and cause of the failure. The failure rate λ_{xzy} defines the transition between state z and state y in architecture x .

Figure 7. Markov chain diagrams of the conversion system architectures.

From Figure 7, the probability of being in state s , denoted as P_{x_s} with $x_s \in \{x_0, x_1, \dots\}$, can be derived for architectures A and B by solving

$$\begin{pmatrix} \lambda_{x01} & -\lambda_{x13} - \lambda_{x14} - \lambda_R & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \lambda_{x02} & 0 & -\lambda_{x23} - \lambda_{x24} - \lambda_R & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_{x13} & \lambda_{x23} & -\lambda_{x34} - \lambda_R & 0 \\ \lambda_{x04} & \lambda_{x14} & \lambda_{x24} & \lambda_{x34} & -\lambda_R \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} P_{x0} \\ P_{x1} \\ P_{x2} \\ P_{x3} \\ P_{x4} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (37)$$

and for architectures C and D by solving

$$\begin{pmatrix} \lambda_{x01} & -\lambda_R \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} P_{x0} \\ P_{x1} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (38)$$

Then, the system failure rate for each architecture is computed as

$$\begin{cases} \lambda_A = \lambda_{A04} \cdot P_{A0} + \lambda_{A14} \cdot P_{A1} + \lambda_{A24} \cdot P_{A2} + \lambda_{A34} \cdot P_{A3} \\ \lambda_B = \lambda_{B04} \cdot P_{B0} + \lambda_{B14} \cdot P_{B1} + \lambda_{B24} \cdot P_{B2} + \lambda_{B34} \cdot P_{B3} \\ \lambda_C = \lambda_{C01} \cdot P_{C0} \\ \lambda_D = \lambda_{D01} \cdot P_{D0} . \end{cases} \quad (39)$$

7. PCS cost model

This section presents the cost model used in the optimization process to compute the capital and operational cost of the PCS. The model includes the capital cost of semiconductors, magnetic elements, capacitors, heatsinks and fans, and auxiliary electronics, as well as the maintenance and penalty costs.

7.1. Semiconductors cost model

The cost of power semiconductor devices is primarily influenced by the size of the device chip and the package [17]. Therefore, the total cost of these devices in a given conversion architecture is defined as

$$\sigma_{SC} = \sum_k \sigma_{SC,k} = \sum_k \left(\sigma'_{chip,k} \cdot A_{chip,k} + \sigma_{pack,k} \right), \quad (40)$$

where $\sigma'_{chip,k}$ is device k specific cost per chip area $A_{chip,k}$ which depends on the chip technology and $\sigma_{pack,k}$ is the price of the device package. The values for $\sigma'_{chip,k}$ and $\sigma_{pack,k}$ are obtained from [6,17]. The chip area can be derived from the electrical characteristics of the device. For instance, in unipolar power devices, such as MOSFETs, the chip area of a specific device can be determined from its on-state resistance as

$$A_{chip,k} = \frac{K_{r,k} \cdot U_{rt,k}^{\alpha_{r,k}}}{r_{ds,on,k}} \quad (41)$$

where $U_{rt,x,k}^{\alpha_{r,k}}$ is the device voltage rating, and $K_{r,k}$ and $\alpha_{r,k}$ are scaling factors that depend on the unipolar device technology. The values for $K_{r,k}$ and $\alpha_{r,k}$ are obtained from [18].

7.2. Magnetics cost model

The cost of magnetic components is determined by the material costs of the components and the labor costs involved in their manufacturing process [19]. Thus, the total cost of the magnetic components in a given conversion architecture is

$$\sigma_{L,tot} = \sum_k (\sigma_{c,k} + \sigma_{W,k} + \sigma_{lab,k}), \quad (42)$$

where $\sigma_{c,k}$ is the material cost associated to the core and $\sigma_{W,k}$ is the cost associated to the windings, coil formers and connectors, and $\sigma_{lab,k}$ is the labour cost, all referred to magnetic component k .

The core material cost $\sigma_{c,k}$ is defined as

$$\sigma_{c,k} = \sigma'_{c,k} \cdot W_{c,k} \cdot N_{c,k} + \sigma_{c,fc,k} \cdot N_{c,k}, \quad (43)$$

where $\sigma'_{c,k}$ is the core material specific cost, $W_{c,k}$ is the weight of a single core, $N_{c,k}$ is the number of stacked cores, and $\sigma_{c,fc,k}$ is the core fix cost, all referred to magnetic component k . The winding cost $\sigma_{W,k}$ is defined as

$$\sigma_{W,k} = \sum_j \left(\sigma'_{W,k,j} \cdot W_{W,k,j} \right) + \sigma_{W,fc,k}, \quad (44)$$

where $\sigma'_{W,k,j}$ is the winding j material specific cost, $W_{W,k,j}$ is winding j weight, and $\sigma_{W,fc,k}$ is the fix cost related to the coil formers, all referred to magnetic component k . The labour cost $\sigma_{lab,k}$ is defined as

$$\sigma_{lab,k} = \sigma'_{lab,k} \cdot \sum_j W_{W,k,j} + \sigma_{lab,fc,k}, \quad (45)$$

where $\sigma'_{lab,k}$ and $\sigma_{lab,fc,k}$ are the labour specific cost and fixed cost, respectively, all referred to magnetic component k . The material and labour specific and fixed costs for magnetic elements are obtained from [17,19].

7.3. Capacitors cost model

This analysis focuses on two dominant types of power capacitors commonly employed in power electronics: metallized polypropylene thin-film capacitors (MKP) and aluminum electrolytic capacitors (Al ELCO).

Al ELCO capacitors are primarily used in LF applications, whereas metallized polypropylene (MKP) film capacitors are employed for HF applications. The cost model for LF and HF capacitors is defined in [17] as

$$\sigma_{C,tot} = \sum_k \sigma_{LF,k} + \sum_k \sigma_{HF,k}, \quad (46)$$

where $\sigma_{LF,k}$ is the unitary cost of an ELCO capacitor, and $\sigma_{HF,k}$ is the unitary cost of a MKP film capacitor. Both unitary costs, $\sigma_{LF,k}$ and $\sigma_{HF,k}$, are defined as

$$\sigma_{LF,k} = \beta_{LF} \cdot U_{LF,k} + \gamma_{LF} \cdot C_{LF,k} \cdot U_{LF,k}^2, \quad (47)$$

$$\sigma_{HF,k} = \alpha_{HF} + \beta_{HF} \cdot U_{HF,k} + \gamma_{HF} \cdot C_{HF,k} \quad (48)$$

where $U_{x,k}$ is the k capacitor rated voltage, $C_{x,k}$ is the k capacitor rated capacitance, and β_x , γ_x and α_x are the coefficients of the cost model establishing the relation between $U_{x,k}$, $C_{x,k}$, and the unit cost of an ELCO and MKP film capacitors.

7.4. Heatsinks and fans cost model

This study considers extruded heatsinks, which, as detailed in [17], exhibit a pronounced linear correlation between their cost and envelope volume. The envelope volume is determined by the heatsink's profile area and extrusion length. Consequently, the overall cost of the heatsink components can be expressed as

$$\sigma_{hs,tot} = \sum_k \left(\sigma_{hs,fc,k} + \sigma'_{hs,k} \cdot V_{hs,k} \right), \quad (49)$$

where $\sigma_{hs,fc,k}$ and $\sigma'_{hs,k}$ are the fix and specific costs referred to the extruded heatsink component k .

The cost of a fan can be regarded as largely independent of its rated airflow within the range of 600 lfm to 800 lfm, as indicated by manufacturer data presented in [17]. The data reveals a negligible correlation between fan price and maximum airflow. Instead, the cost exhibits a linear dependence on the fan volume, which can be expressed as

$$\sigma_{fan,tot} = \sum_k \left(\sigma_{fan,fc,k} + \sigma'_{fan,k} \cdot V_{fan,k} \right), \quad (50)$$

where $\sigma_{fan,fc,k}$ is the fix cost and $\sigma'_{fan,k}$ is the specific cost per volume.

Then, considering one fan is used for each heatsink, the total cost of the cooling system is defined as

$$\sigma_{CS,tot} = \sum_k \left(\sigma_{hs,fc,k} + \sigma'_{hs,k} \cdot V_{hs,k} + \sigma_{fan,fc,k} + \sigma'_{fan,k} \cdot V_{fan,k} \right). \quad (51)$$

7.5. Auxiliary electronics cost model

The cost of the auxiliary electronics is determined by the quantity of gate drivers, voltage sensors, and current sensors, along with their respective unit prices [19]. Then, the auxiliary electronics cost is

$$\sigma_{\text{aux}} = N_{\text{GD}} \cdot \sigma_{\text{GD}} + N_{\text{VS}} \cdot \sigma_{\text{VS}} + N_{\text{IS}} \cdot \sigma_{\text{IS}}, \quad (52)$$

where N_{GD} , N_{VS} and N_{IS} are the number of gate drivers, voltage sensors and current sensors, and σ_{GD} , σ_{VS} , and σ_{IS} are the unit cost of the gate drivers, the voltage sources and the current sources.

7.6. Operational cost model

The operational cost of a power system is determined by two factors: the repair costs associated with converter failures and the revenue loss due to undelivered energy caused by partial or complete converter outages, categorized as maintenance costs and penalty costs, respectively.

The cost associated with undelivered power is calculated using a penalty cost σ'_{pen} . The capital cost associated to each repair is divided into the material cost (σ_{mat}) and the labour cost (σ_{lab}). For each failure, the repair duration is assumed to be 7 days, with 8 hours of work per day. Therefore, being $S_{\text{lost},x,s}$ the power not delivered in the state s by the power conversion system architecture x , and considering 8760 hours per year, the power conversion system failure cost for architecture x is

$$\sigma_{\text{fail},x} = 8760 \cdot \sum_s P_{x,s} \cdot \left(\sigma'_{\text{pen}} \cdot S_{\text{lost},x,s} + \frac{\lambda_R}{10^6} \cdot (\sigma_{\text{lab}} \cdot 7 \cdot 8 + \sigma_{\text{mat}}) \right). \quad (53)$$

8. Multiobjective optimization

8.1. Objective function and weighting strategy

To achieve an optimal trade-off in terms of losses (ζ) and cost (σ) of the PCS, a multiobjective function is defined as

$$G_{x,w}(\mathbf{y}) = W_{\zeta w} \cdot \zeta'_{x,w}(\mathbf{y}) + W_{\sigma w} \cdot \sigma'_{x,w}(\mathbf{y}), \quad (54)$$

where \mathbf{y} is the vector containing the optimization variables (y_i), $\zeta'_{x,w} = \zeta_{x,w} / \zeta_b$ and $\sigma'_{x,w} = \sigma_{x,w} / \sigma_b$ are the per-unit losses and cost for architecture x and weight set w , normalized by the base values ζ_b and σ_b , and $W_{\zeta w}$ and $W_{\sigma w}$ are user-defined weights ranging $[0, 1]$, with $W_{\zeta w} + W_{\sigma w} = 1, \forall w$. These weights enable the exploration of the $\zeta - \sigma$ Pareto fronts for each architecture, accounting for varying priorities between efficiency and cost.

Three Pareto fronts are obtained by minimizing $G_{x,w}$ for each architecture using three different combinations of weight sets:

- Weight set 1 (WS1): $\{W_{\zeta 1}, W_{\sigma 1}\} = \{0.5, 0.5\}$. Losses and cost reduction are equally prioritized.
- Weight set 2 (WS2): $\{W_{\zeta 2}, W_{\sigma 2}\} = \{0.2, 0.8\}$. Cost reduction is prioritized.
- Weight set 3 (WS3): $\{W_{\zeta 3}, W_{\sigma 3}\} = \{0.8, 0.2\}$. Losses reduction is prioritized.

The optimization process aims to minimize $G_{x,w}$ for each architecture and weight set considering a total of 81 optimization variables. Constraints are imposed to the optimization variables and to the results of intermediate calculations to ensure that the solutions are feasible and meet the system's operational requirements. The optimization variables, along with the main constraints, are described in Appendix A.

8.2. Optimization problem solver and setup

The multiobjective optimization problem is solved using MATLAB's *surrogateopt* solver, which is well-suited for global minimization of time-consuming objective functions.

Given a group of initial points $\{y_{0,1}, y_{0,2}, \dots, y_{0,Nip}\}$ handed to the solver, where Nip is the number of initial points, surrogateopt builds a surrogate model by interpolation. Candidate points are then evaluated using a merit function, and the best one is incorporated into the model. The solver halts after a predefined number of variable combinations have been evaluated. Since the initial points significantly influence solution optimality, surrogateopt is run 6 times per architecture and weight set, providing a different set of initial points each time, with $Nip = 4$ for each run. These initial points are manually selected to ensure feasibility. In total, the solver is executed 72 times across all architectures and weight sets.

8.3. Optimization results

Executing the *surrogate* optimization solver on each architecture resulted in 7,415 feasible solutions for architecture A, 20,174 for architecture B, 8,966 for architecture C, and 41,120 for architecture D.

Figure 8 presents a comparison of the results in terms of losses and cost for each architecture and weight set. Solutions closer to the origin present a lower objective function value, with optimum solutions highlighted in black and white markers. The objective function, cost, and losses for these solutions are listed in Table 2. Additionally, the Pareto front for each architecture and weight set is depicted, defined by the equipotential line where the objective function matches the optimum value in the $\zeta - \sigma$ plane. The optimization results highlight a clear cost-loss trade-off across all weight sets and architectures. The comparison between architectures reveals that lower parallelization leads to better results. For instance, the lower the number of dc-dc and dc-ac modules, the lower the cost achieved for WS2 (cost prioritization). Moreover, the lower the number of dc-ac modules, the lower the losses achieved with WS3 (losses prioritization). When equally prioritizing cost and losses (WS1), architectures C and D are clearly superior to architectures A and B, achieving slightly lower losses with a much-reduced cost. Overall, architecture D stands as the optimum system architecture, since the three weight-set optimum solutions feature lower cost and losses to the rest of architectures.

Figure 8. Losses and cost values obtained with the top 10% best results for each architecture and weight set. Pareto front lines for the optimum solutions shown in dotted lines. Optimum solutions shown with black and white markers.

Table 2. Values of the objective function, cost, and losses provided by the optimum solution for each architecture and weight set.

Architecture	Weight set	$G_{x,w}$ [p.u.]	$\sigma'_{x,w}$ [p.u.]	$\zeta'_{x,w}$ [p.u.]
A	WS1	2.80	3.96	1.64
	WS2	3.44	3.82	1.91
	WS3	1.96	4.85	1.24
B	WS1	2.60	3.66	1.53
	WS2	3.18	3.47	2.00
	WS3	1.81	4.55	1.13
C	WS1	2.06	2.63	1.49
	WS2	2.21	2.20	2.10
	WS3	1.66	3.09	1.30
D	WS1	1.75	2.12	1.39
	WS2	1.76	1.76	1.75
	WS3	1.45	2.90	1.09

Figure 9 presents a break down of the cost for the optimum solutions across each architecture and weight set. For all architectures and weight sets the semiconductors

account for almost 50 % of the system cost. The second largest capital cost are magnetic elements, followed closely by the reparation cost, the cooling system cost (heatsinks and fans), and the capacitors cost. The cost of the auxiliary components and the cost penalty from revenue losses are marginal in all cases ($\leq 6\%$).

Overall, architectures C and D feature lower material costs. Although there is some linear dependency of each component cost with its current rating, capacity, thermal resistance, etc., still a fixed cost is present (package cost, labour cost, auxiliary components, etc.) and it is approximately the same for all components of the same type. Therefore, a higher number of components leads to higher system costs, explaining the reduction in capital costs from architectures A to D. However, some exceptions occur. The cost of capacitors decreases when reducing the number of dc-ac converters (architectures A to B and C to D), but increases when reducing the number of dc-dc converters (architectures A to C and B to D). Although the total number of capacitors across the dc-dc converters in architectures A and B is higher than on Architectures C and D, the required total capacitance is lower thanks to the interleaving of the three dc-dc converters, thus reducing the overall capacitor costs.

Regarding the operational costs, the system reparation cost is greater in architectures A and B, mainly because they feature more components, and thus the probability of a failure occurring is greater. The energy revenue loss in all architectures is similar. Thus, having more redundancy does not necessarily mean a lower operation cost derived from failures. Nonetheless, if the penalty cost for total system shutdown is increased, this would increase architectures C and D revenue loss cost, stopping them from being competitive compared to architectures A and B in terms of operational cost.

Figure 10 details the losses of the optimum solutions for each architecture and weight set. In architectures B, C, and D, semiconductor losses dominate (50%-60% of total losses), followed by magnetic losses (35%-45%). Architecture A is an exception, with magnetic losses (50%) exceeding semiconductor losses (45%), due to the reduced magnetic core losses in architectures C and D. These losses are mainly dependent to the battery and HV dc-link voltage, the switching frequency, and the number of cores. The higher these values are, the higher the core losses. Since the voltages and switching frequencies are similar, the greater number of cores in architectures A and B leads to higher core losses.

The most parallelized architectures (C and D) feature on average lower semiconductor conduction losses, since these losses are proportional to the squared RMS current. For instance, if the MOSFETs employed in the dc-dc converters in architectures A and B (with 3 converters) and C and D (with 1 converters) feature the same on-state resistance, the total MOSFET conduction losses in architectures A and B dc-dc modules are approximately one-third of those in C and D. When looking at Figure 23, the average (across WSs) conduction losses across WSs of architectures A and B are actually 5/6 of C and D. This is due to the MOSFETs selected by the optimization algorithm in A and B featuring on average higher on-state resistance than those in C and D, and the dc-dc converters in C and D featuring up to 4 MOSFETs in parallel, reducing effective on-state resistance.

Nonetheless, the magnetic elements' copper losses do not follow this trend. On average across WSs, the copper losses in architectures with two dc-ac converters are larger than those with a single dc-ac converter. This is because the number of turns in Ll inductors increases when the converter power decreases to limit the current total harmonic distortion (THD), resulting in higher copper losses. This can be compensated by increasing the number copper area at the expense of a higher cost.

Overall, architectures A and B feature slightly more switching losses than C and D. However, this trend is inverted when prioritizing the minimization of the losses (WS3). In this solution, the number of MOSFETs in parallel in architectures C and D is higher than in WS1 and WS2, resulting in overall more switching instances, and thus higher switching losses.

In all architectures, capacitor losses are marginal (around 5%).

Figure 9. Cost distribution for the optimum solution on each architecture and weight set.

9. Discussion

This study presents an optimization tool for the design of a PCS in a HESS integrating a LTO battery and an AORF battery to the grid, balancing cost, efficiency, and reliability. The optimization is performed considering four system-architecture candidates featuring different degrees of power-converter parallelization. Moreover, the optimization problem is defined with comprehensive electric, losses, reliability, and cost models of the components in the power converters, and a wide design space is defined to determine the specifications of the different power-converter elements. The optimization targets the minimization of the system conversion losses and cost, where the cost accounts for the capital expenditure, the system failure reparation, and the revenue loss from the energy not delivered due to system partial or complete shutdown caused by failures. A set of optimization problems are defined for each architecture, assigning different priorities to the minimization of losses and cost.

The results obtained from the optimization process show that lower levels of parallelization tend to reduce costs significantly due to a decrease in the number of components,

Figure 10. Losses distribution for the optimum solution on each architecture and weight set.

such as converters, magnetic elements, and capacitors, resulting in low capital and maintenance cost, which can be critical in cost-sensitive applications.

Conversely, architectures with higher parallelization feature higher fault tolerance and operational flexibility. By connecting multiple converters in parallel, these architectures can continue operating under partial failures, ensuring greater reliability.

The results also show the importance of semiconductor and magnetic losses across all architectures. In highly parallelized systems, magnetic core losses are particularly significant due to the increased number of magnetic components, while systems with lower parallelization present higher conduction losses due to higher current density.

For the present HESS, the architecture featuring a single DAB converter per battery and a single three-phase dc-ac converter stands as the optimum solution. Moreover, the solution given by WS2 features the best trade-off in terms of cost and efficiency.

Future work should extend this analysis by considering multiple operation points of the PCS, to enhance the applicability of the optimization process, and experimental validation.

Appendix A

This appendix presents a list of the optimization variables used in the optimization process and their corresponding design space. The optimization-variables set, presented in Table A1, is composed of 81 discrete variables. Each optimization variable can be either numeric (real or integer) or text, and can take values that are part of a set of values defined by the user, that is, the design space. The design-space value sets are presented in A2.

Table A1. Optimization variables.

Parameter	Description
$n_{\text{par,sw,DAB,LV},b}$	Number of switches connected in parallel in the LV side of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$n_{\text{par,sw,DAB,HV},b}$	Number of switches connected in parallel in the HV side of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$n_{\text{par,sw,dc-ac},b}$	Number of switches connected in parallel in the dc-ac converter connected to the b battery
$\text{type}_{\text{sw,DAB,LV,LTO}}$	Type of switch used in the LV side of the DAB converter(s) connected to the LTO battery
$\text{model}_{\text{sw,DAB,LV},b}$	Switch model in the LV side of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$\text{model}_{\text{sw,DAB,HV},b}$	Switch model in the HV side of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$\text{model}_{\text{sw,dc-ac},b}$	Switch model of the dc-ac converter connected to the b battery
V_{HV}	HV dc link voltage
$f_{\text{s,DAB},b}$	Switching frequency of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$m_{f,b}$	mf factor for the dc-ac converter connected to the b battery
$\text{model}_{\text{HS,DAB,LV},b}$	Heatsink model to dissipate the heat generated by the switches in the LV side of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$\text{model}_{\text{HS,DAB,HV},b}$	Heatsink model to dissipate the heat generated by the switches in the HV side of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$\text{model}_{\text{HS,dc-ac},b}$	Heatsink model to dissipate the heat generated by the switches of the dc-ac converter connected to the b battery
$L_{\text{HS,DAB,LV},b}$	Length of the heatsink for the switches in the LV side of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$L_{\text{HS,DAB,HV},b}$	Length of the heatsink for the switches in the HV side of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$L_{\text{HS,dc-ac},b}$	Length of the heatsink for the switches of the dc-ac converter connected to the b battery

Parameter	Description
$n_{\text{par, cap, LV, } b}$	Number of parallel capacitors in the LV side of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$n_{\text{par, cap, HV, } b}$	Number of parallel capacitors in the HV dc link between the DAB converter(s) and the dc-ac converter connected to the b battery
$model_{\text{cap, LV, } b}$	Capacitor model in the LV side of the DAB connected to the b battery
$model_{\text{cap, HV, } b}$	Capacitor model in the HV side of the DAB connected to the b battery
$n_{\text{core, L, DAB, } b}$	Number of cores stacked in parallel in the inductor in the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$n_{\text{core, Tx, DAB, } b}$	Number of cores stacked in parallel in the transformer in the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$n_{\text{core, L, dc-ac, } b}$	Number of cores stacked in parallel in the inductors of the dc-ac converter connected to the b battery
$model_{\text{core, L, DAB, } b}$	Core model in the inductor of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$model_{\text{core, Tx, DAB, } b}$	Core model in the transformer of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$model_{\text{core, L, dc-ac, } b}$	Core model in the inductors of the dc-ac converter connected to the b battery
$type_{\text{wire, L, DAB, } b}$	Wire type used in the inductor of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$type_{\text{wire, Tx, DAB, } b}$	Wire type used in the transformer of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$type_{\text{wire, L, dc-ac, } b}$	Wire type used in the inductors of the dc-ac converter connected to the b battery
$model_{\text{wire, L, DAB, } b}$	Wire model used in the inductor of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$model_{\text{wire, Tx, DAB, } b}$	Wire model used in the transformer of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$model_{\text{wire, L, dc-ac, } b}$	Wire model used in the inductors of the dc-ac converter connected to the b battery
$n_{\text{t, L, DAB, } b}$	Number of turns in the inductor of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$n_{\text{t, Tx, DAB, } b}$	Number of turns in the transformer of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery

Parameter	Description
$n_{t,L,dc-ac,b}$	Number of turns in the inductors of the dc-ac converter connected to the b battery
$npw_{L,DAB,b}$	Number of parallel conductors in the inductor of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$npw_{Tx,DAB,LV,b}$	Number of parallel conductors in the LV side of the transformer of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$npw_{Tx,DAB,HV,b}$	Number of parallel conductors in the HV side of the transformer of the DAB converter(s) connected to the b battery
$npw_{L,dc-ac,b}$	Number of parallel conductors in the inductor of the dc-ac converter connected to the b battery

Table A2. Design space.

Parameter	Design space
$n_{par,sw,DAB,LV,b}$	1 to 4
$n_{par,sw,DAB,HV,b}$	Up to 2
$n_{par,sw,dc-ac,b}$	Up to 2
$type_{sw,DAB,LV,LTO}$	Discrete Si MOSFET, Discrete SiC MOSFET
$model_{sw,DAB,LV,b}$	<p><u>LTO battery:</u></p> <p>- Si MOSFET: <i>IRF100P218, IRF100P219, IPP023N10N5, IPP030N10N5, STF150N10F7, IPB120N10S4-03, SUP70090E, IPD122N10N3G, IPP126N10N3G</i></p> <p>- SiC MOSFET: <i>UF3SC065007K4S</i></p> <p><u>AORF battery:</u></p> <p>Si MOSFET: <i>SiHG018N60E, SiHG026N60EF, IPZ60R017C7, IPW60R017C7, IPW60R018CFD7, IPW60R024CFD7, IPW60R024P7, IPZA60R024P7, IPW60R041P6, IPW60R060P7</i></p>
$model_{sw,DAB,HV,b}$	SiC MOSFET modules: <i>CAB006M12GM3, CAB008M12GM3, CAB011M12FM3, CAB016M12FM3</i>
$model_{sw,dc-ac,b}$	SiC MOSFET modules: <i>CAB006M12GM3, CAB008M12GM3, CAB011M12FM3, CAB016M12FM3, CCB021M12FM3, CCB032M12FM3</i>
V_{HV}	700 V, 750 V, 800 V
$f_{s,DAB,b}$	20 kHz, 24 kHz, . . . , 92 kHz, 96 kHz, 100 kHz
$m_{f,b}$	201, 219, 237, . . . , 687, 705, 723
$model_{HS,DAB,LV,b}$	

Parameter	Design space
$model_{HS,DAB,HV,b}$	From Advanced Thermal Solutions extrusion heat sinks catalogue: ATS-EXL6, ATS-EXL59, ATS-EXL66, ATS-EXL67, ATS-EXL68, ATS-EXL75
$model_{HS,dc-ac,b}$	
$L_{HS,DAB,LV,b}$	2 to 8 inches
$L_{HS,DAB,HV,b}$	
$L_{HS,dc-ac,b}$	
$n_{par,cap,LV,b}$	1 to 8
$n_{par,cap,HV,b}$	
$model_{cap,LV,b}$	<p><u>LTO battery:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - From Cornell Dobilier Electronics film capacitors: 935C1W3K-F, 935C1W20K-F, 935C1W30K-F - From Cornell TDK film capacitors: B32529 <p><u>AORF battery:</u></p> <p>From Cornell Dobilier Electronics film capacitors: UNL6W30K-F, UNL6W80K-F, UNL7W20K-F, UNL7W50K-F</p>
$model_{cap,HV,b}$	From Cornell Dobilier Electronics film capacitors: 947D152K901DLRSN, 947C102K901DCHS, 947D112K102DLRSN, 947C641K102DBHS, 947C321K122DAHS, 944U101K122AC, 944U660K102AA
$n_{core,L,DAB,b}$	1 to 5
$n_{core,Tx,DAB,b}$	1 to 5
$n_{core,L,dc-ac,b}$	1 to 5
$model_{core,L,DAB,b}$	- From Magnetics cores catalogue: 0077164A7 (Powdercore), 0077169A7 (Powdercore), 0077101A7 (Powdercore), 0077336A7 (Powdercore), 0077614A7 (Powdercore), 0077869A7 (Powdercore), 0059188A2 (Edge), 0059909A2 (Edge), 0077327A7 (Powdercore)
$model_{core,Tx,DAB,b}$	- From Magnetics cores catalogue: 00K114LE060 (Powdercore), 0077740A7 (Powdercore), 0077778A7 (Powdercore), 0077098A7 (Powdercore), 00K160LE026 (Powdercore), 0077339A7 (Powdercore), 00K8038U026 (Powdercore), 0077165A7 (Powdercore), 0077169A7 (Powdercore)
$model_{core,L,dc-ac,b}$	- From Magnetics and TDK Electronics cores catalogue: E32/16/11 (Ferrite), 00K3112U090 (Powdercore), 00K114LE014 (Powdercore), 0077740A7 (Powdercore), 0077778A7 (Powdercore), 00K114LE060 (Powdercore), 0077620A7 (Powdercore), 0077098A7 (Powdercore), 00K160LE026 (Powdercore), 0077339A7 (Powdercore), 00K8038U026 (Powdercore), 0077165A7 (Powdercore)
$type_{wire,L,DAB,b}$	Round, Foil, Litz

Parameter	Design space
$type_{\text{wire,Tx,DAB},b}$	Round, Foil, Litz
$type_{\text{wire,L,DAB},b}$	Round, Foil, Litz
$model_{\text{wire,L,DAB},b}$	- Round wires: 2 AWG to 30 AWG - Litz wires: from 0.04 mm diameter strand and 45 conductors per litz, to 0.28 mm diameter strand and 1350 conductors per litz
$model_{\text{wire,Tx,DAB},b}$	
$model_{\text{wire,L,DAB},b}$	
$n_{t,L,DAB,b}$	Up to 80 turns
$n_{t,Tx,DAB,b}$	Up to 80 turns
$n_{t,L,dc-ac,b}$	Up to 80 turns
$npw_{L,DAB,b}$	Up to 8 conductors
$npw_{Tx,DAB,LV,b}$	Up to 8 conductors
$npw_{Tx,DAB,HV,b}$	Up to 8 conductors
$npw_{L,dc-ac,b}$	Up to 8 conductors

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